

Harvesting Energy from Living Aquatic Plants

(Perolehan Tenaga daripada Tumbuh-Tumbuhan Akuatik)

Pek Yee Teoh, Ramizi bin Mohamed

Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia

ABSTRACT

In today's world, electricity is said to be a necessity as anything as small as mobile phone or as large as a power distribution system requires electricity to function. Electricity can be produced through both renewable and non-renewable sources. With the increasing trend in demand of electricity, more fossil fuels need to be burnt which eventually lead to serious pollution. Harvesting energy from living plants is considered as a new green approach to obtain electricity whereas this paper narrows down the types of plants to aquatic plants only. Photosynthesis carried out by all living plants will produce organic matters such as glucose. Excess glucose will be excreted out through roots and this process is known as Rhizodeposition process. Naturally occurring microbes will disintegrate the extra glucose, releasing electrons which will then be converted into electricity. This paper aims to determine the best design that can harvest highest voltage. Devil's Ivy or *Epipremnum aureum* is chosen as the experimental plant such that it is an aquatic plant that meets the prerequisite for P-MFC. Three models are set up. First and second models are alike where different pair of electrodes are being used. As for third model, it is a Planted Sediment Microbial Fuel Cell (PSMFC). PSMFC combines the concept of both P-MFC and SMFC, provided PSMFC does not require membrane. A resistor is used as load and the circuits for respective model are illustrated. Results have shown that model with Zn-Cu as electrodes is able to produce the highest voltage and current among the other designs, approximately 155.00mV and 127.50 μ A per pot, followed by PSMFC and model with graphite as electrodes produces the least voltage and current.

Keywords: Electricity; Aquatic Plants; Voltage; Electrodes; PSMFC

ABSTRAK

Dalam dunia masa kini, elektrik dikatakan sebagai satu keperluan yang amat penting. Hal ini disebabkan oleh benda sekecil telefon bimbit atau sebesar sistem pengagihan kuasa memerlukan tenaga elektrik untuk berfungsi. Tenaga elektrik dapat diperolehi daripada dua sumber tenaga, iaitu sumber tenaga yang boleh diperbaharui dan yang tidak boleh diperbaharui. Dengan trend permintaan tenaga elektrik yang semakin meningkat, lebih banyak bahan bakar fosil perlu dibakar dan menyebabkan kadar pencemaran semakin serius. Perolehan tenaga daripada tumbuh-tumbuhan dianggap sebagai pendekatan hijau yang baru untuk mendapatkan tenaga elektrik di mana kajian ini memberi fokus kepada jenis tumbuhan akuatik sahaja. Fotosintesis yang dilakukan oleh tumbuh-tumbuhan akan menghasilkan sebatian organik. Sebatian organik seperti glukosa yang berlebihan akan dikeluarkan melalui akar dan proses ini dikenali sebagai proses Rhizodeposition. Mikrob yang berada di sekitar akar akan menguraikan glukosa lebih tersebut, membebaskan elektron yang kemudiannya diubah sebagai tenaga elektrik. Kajian ini bertujuan untuk menentukan model terbaik yang dapat mengeluarkan voltan tertinggi. Devil's Ivy atau *Epipremnum aureum* dipilih sebagai tumbuhan eksperimen sebab ia merupakan tumbuhan air yang memenuhi prasyarat untuk P-MFC. Tiga model telah disediakan. Model pertama dan kedua adalah lebih kurang sama di mana pasangan elektrod yang digunakan adalah berlainan kombinasi. Bagi model ketiga, ia adalah *Planted Sediment Microbial Fuel Cell* (PSMFC). PSMFC menggabungkan konsep kedua-dua P-MFC dan SMFC, dengan syarat PSMFC tidak memerlukan membran. Satu perintang telah digunakan sebagai beban. Litar-itar bagi ketiga-tiga model telah digambarkan. Hasil kajian telah menunjukkan bahawa model yang menggunakan Zn-Cu sebagai elektrod mampu menghasilkan voltan dan arus tertinggi, iaitu sebanyak 155.00mV dan 127.50 μ A per pasu, diikuti oleh PSMFC dan model yang menggunakan grafit sebagai elektrod menghasilkan voltan dan arus paling sikit.

Kata Kunci: Tenaga Elektrik; Tumbuh-Tumbuhan Akuatik; Voltan; Elektrod; PSMFC

INTRODUCTION

With the technology advancement in today’s world, nearly everything is operated by electricity. Electricity plays an essential role in humans’ everyday lifestyle. Electricity is a form of energy which can be acquired through different energy resources. There are two types of energy resources, i.e. primary and secondary energy resources. (Resourcefulness, n.d.) Primary energy resources can be classified into two large categories which are renewable and non-renewable energy. Renewable energy is energy that can be replenished and always exists such as solar energy, wind energy and tidal energy. On the other hand, non-renewable energy is that which will be used up one day. For instance, fossil fuels like coal, natural gas and petroleum. As for secondary energy resources, they are the transformation from primary energy resources a.k.a. energy carriers. These energy carriers such as electricity, petrol and hydrogen are directly usable and not as dangerous as primary energy resources.

The most common secondary energy resource to be seen is electricity. It can be obtained from primary energy resources. Substances such as coals, natural gas or oil will be exploited and transported to power stations. Usually, power stations will generate electricity by burning them. The electricity produced will be distributed through transmission lines to the designated destinations for residential or industrial purposes. One of the most concerning effects as a result from burning of fossil fuels is the emission of Carbon Dioxide (CO₂). CO₂ has no doubt that it brings several effects to humans as well as mother Earth. Alongside with today’s technology, the average energy consumption for daily lifestyle increases with the population increment. As to sustain this massive requirement, more electricity is meant to be produced. Hence, more fossil fuels will have to be burnt and transformed to electricity for human’s usage. More CO₂ will be emitted. Increases in the concentration of CO₂ will increase the Earth’s temperature. (Effects of Changing The Carbon Cycle, 2011) This phenomenon is known as Greenhouse warming. CO₂ traps the heat within Earth, causing the glaciers in both North Pole and South Pole to melt at a very fast rate. Sea level will then increase in height every year. (Glick, n.d.) Apart from that, the air quality deteriorates every day and it is harmful to humans. Problems such as migraines and nausea might occur for certain individuals. The high concentration of CO₂ in air eventually causes breathing difficulties, leading to asthma, heart attacks and worse, death. Studies have proven that in China, approximately 1 million deaths as a result of air pollution is reported annually. (Hong et al. 2019)

In conjunction with these alarming conditions, a green approach has been developed and is in its rising stage. It makes use of the nature’s gift; the plants. Plants are everywhere. Forests, paddy fields or a small bonsai can be used to generate electricity. It is no doubt that every plant will carry out photosynthesis. Photosynthesis is considered as an endothermic reaction where CO₂ and sunlight are required. Organic substances such as glucose will be formed and a small amount will be used for plants’ growth. Rhizodeposition process will take place where there will be excretion of exudates (glucose), secretion (enzymes), lysates (dead cell) and air (ethylene) from the roots. (Melek & Aytun 2007)

Numerous methods have been discovered by different researchers in obtaining electricity from plants. Electricity can be generated through the movement of leaves. Figure 1 shows the generation of electricity from movement of leaves with the help of piezoelectric transducer. The transducer is attached at both leaves and stem. Once movement is sensed, piezoelectric capacitor will be triggered and voltage is produced. (Teng et al. 2018)

FIGURE 1. Electricity from Wind Energy

Source : (Teng et al. 2018)

Studies have shown that one leaf is able to generate up to 150V and light up 100 LEDs. (Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia - IIT, 2018) A hybrid plant system is developed. Dielectrics are attached on both upper and lower epidermis of leaf. Voltage will be recorded if movement is observed. (Meder et al. 2018) Figure 2 shows the concept of acquiring electricity from cuticles.

FIGURE 2. Electricity from Plants' Cuticles

Source : (Meder et al. 2018)

Another method to acquire electricity is by directly embedding electrodes into the stem of plants as shown in Figure 3. This allows flow of ions and electricity will be generated. Research has showed that copper and zinc as electrodes together with aloe vera can produce the most voltage. A relationship between number of pairs of electrodes and voltage produced has been proven. Voltage produced is able to power up some low power consumption appliances. (Choo et al. 2013)

FIGURE 3. Embedment of Electrodes in Stem

Source : (Choo et al. 2013)

Plant-Microbial Fuel Cell (P-MFC) is another way to obtain electricity from living plants. Figure 4 shows an example of P-MFC. P-MFC utilizes the plants and naturally occurring bacteria to produce electricity. When organic matter is produced from photosynthesis, approximately 70% of them will be excreted into the soil. Naturally occurring bacteria will disintegrate, thus electrons and protons will be released. Electrons will travel to anode whereas protons will diffused through specific membrane to reach cathode. (Helder n.d.)

FIGURE 4. P-MFC

Source : (Helder n.d.)

Sediment Microbial Fuel Cell (SMFC) has similar concept as P-MFC. Due to the membrane used in P-MFC is expensive, SMFC does not require membrane. In SMFC, anode is buried into sediment as to achieve anoxic condition where dissolved oxygen (DO) level is extremely low. As for cathode, it is placed in water where level of DO is relatively high. (Xu et al. 2015) The electro-potential differences between anoxic and oxic condition causes electricity to be produced. (Sajana et al. 2013) Figure 5 illustrates a SMFC.

FIGURE 5. SMFC

Source : (Xu et al. 2015)

Planted Sediment Microbial Fuel Cell (PSMFC) is a combination of both P-MFC and SMFC. A model of PSMFC can be seen in Figure 6. Study has showed that the depth of anode buried has a direct relationship with concentration of oxygen, thus the voltage produced will be varied. (Liu et al. 2018)

FIGURE 6. PSMFC

Source : (Liu et al. 2018)

The objective of this paper is to determine the best design which can harvest the most voltage from living plants besides understanding the concept of plant producing electricity.

METHODOLOGY

Three models of different designs are prepared. Model 1 and Model 2 resemble galvanic cells in which they are dependent on redox reactions for voltage production. As for Model 3, it is designated based on PSMFC. Elements that are required for each design will be listed out in detail in the following part.

Model 1 and Model 2

In preparing Model 1 and 2, a few things need to be prepared beforehand. These 2 models are of same design, but different pair of electrodes are used. Two empty and identical containers are prepared and labelled well; one as Model 1 and the other as Model 2. Approximately 450ml of distilled water is poured into the container. Devil’s Ivy is then being put into each container. Electrodes that will be used which are graphite, zinc and copper are prepared as in Figure 7.

FIGURE 7. Type of Electrodes (Zinc, Copper and Graphite)

For Model 1, graphite is used as both anode and cathode. Model 2 on the other hand, uses zinc as its anode and copper as its cathode. Crocodile wires are used to connect the electrodes to resistor that acts as load and to multimeter for measurement purpose. These two models are left for 3 days in a shady place before the measurements are taken. Figure 8 and Figure 9 represent Model 1 and Model 2 respectively.

FIGURE 8. Model 1

FIGURE 9. Model 2

Model 3

Model 3 is a PSMFC. An empty container is prepared and labelled as Model 3. Underground soil is collected and put into the container. A stainless-steel scrubber that acts as anode is then placed in and covered with another layer of soil; as to create anoxic condition. A crocodile wire is connected to the stainless-steel scrubber. Devil’s Ivy is being planted and gravels are added into the container subsequently. The stem of Devil’s Ivy is later wrapped with steel wool. Another crocodile wire is connected to steel wool. Activated carbon is

filled around the steel wool until fully covered. Distilled water is then added into the container until everything is immersed. The model is left for three days before taking measurements. Figure 10 shows Model 3.

FIGURE 10. Model 3

A 4-band resistor is used as load in this paper which the resistance value is recorded as 975Ω as shown in Figure 11. The three models will be connected to the same resistor in order to record the voltage and current produced.

FIGURE 11. Value of Resistor Used

UNI-T UT139C Digital Multimeter is used to obtain voltage and current readings. The circuit as in Figure 12, Figure 13 and Figure 14 represent the connection of multimeter when taking reading of voltage and current.

FIGURE 12. Circuit for Model 1

FIGURE 13. Circuit for Model 2

FIGURE 14. Circuit for Model 3

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three models were set up in this paper. Each of them is shown in Figure 15, Figure 16 as well as Figure 17.

FIGURE 15. Model 1

FIGURE 16. Model 2

FIGURE 17. Model 3

With the help of digital multimeter, both voltage and current reading for the three models can be recorded. Comparison among three models will be made in the following section.

Voltage Reading

Both minimum and maximum voltage for respective model are recorded. Model 1 is able to produce voltage around 0.05mV and 0.06mV, whereas Model 2 recorded minimum voltage as 154.00mV and maximum voltage at 156.00mV. For Model 3, a reading of 107.30mV is recorded as minimum voltage and maximum voltage is 107.40mV. Table 1 will show the summary of voltage readings for the three models. Average voltage is calculated as to ease the process of comparison.

TABLE 1. Voltage Readings for Three Models

Type of Model	Minimum Voltage (mV)	Maximum Voltage (mV)	Average Voltage (mV)
Model 1	0.05	0.06	0.055
Model 2	154.00	156.00	155.000
Model 3	107.30	107.40	107.350

Current Reading

Current generated by these three models are small which lie within the range of microampere (μA). Both minimum and maximum current for respective model are jotted down. Current produced by Model 1 is recorded as 0.00 μA , whereas Model 2 recorded minimum current as

126.50 μA and maximum current at 128.50 μA . As for Model 3, a reading of 89.20 μA is recorded as the minimum current and maximum current is 89.30 μA . Table 2 will show the summary of current readings for the three models. Average current is calculated as to ease the process of comparison.

TABLE 2. Current Readings for Three Models

Type of Model	Minimum Current (μA)	Maximum Current (μA)	Average Current (μA)
Model 1	0.00	0.00	0.00
Model 2	126.50	128.50	127.50
Model 3	89.20	89.30	89.25

Theory

Referring to Table 1 and Table 2 above, it can be concluded that Model 2 is able to produce the most

energy, followed by Model 3 and Model 1 produces the least energy.

As mentioned earlier, plants will convert solar energy which is abundant into electricity. Plants will carry out photosynthesis with the presence of CO₂ where organic matter such as glucose will be produced as the side products. Plants only require a little amount of glucose for self-usage. Excess glucose will eventually be excreted out through roots. This process is known as Rhizodeposition process. Naturally occurring microbes at the roots will then disintegrate the excess glucose. Electrons will be released.

The theory explained above will be experienced by all three models. However, a clear difference in voltage and current reading is observed.

Model 2 uses zinc and copper as electrodes. Zinc and copper are the examples of

active electrodes which will create an electrode potential difference. Table 3 shows electrode potential specifically for both zinc and copper (Antelman & Harris 1982). Redox reaction is expected to occur between this combination of electrodes. In this case, zinc will act as anode and undergo oxidation process as in Equation (1). While on the contrary, copper will behave as cathode and reduction as stated in Equation (2) will occur.

Electrons will be released by zinc. Copper will take in the electrons. According to Table 3 and also Equation (3), Model 2 supposedly produces voltage around 1.10V. However, the internal resistance within the cell as well as the load has caused the voltage produced to be 155.00mV.

TABLE 3. Electrode Potential
Source : (Antelman & Harris 1982)

Metal	Half Equation	Potential (V)
Copper	$Cu^{2+} + 2e^{-} \rightarrow Cu$	+0.34
Zinc	$Zn^{2+} + 2e^{-} \rightarrow Zn$	-0.76

Conversely, Model 3 combines the concept of P-MFC and SMFC. The anode is buried in the sediment. This is to produce an anoxic condition for anode. Anoxic condition is defined as a surrounding where dissolved oxygen (DO) level is extremely low. This model is closed with air cathode where the DO level is high. PSMFC is dependent on the difference of concentration in DO level. Electrons resulted from the break down process of glucose will be used for oxygen reduction in cathode. Equation (4) shows the oxygen reduction process.

$$E_{cell} = E_{cathode} - E_{anode} \tag{3}$$

Model 1 generated the least voltage and current among all. Electrodes pair used in Model 1 is of the same material which are graphite. Graphite is an example of inert electrodes where redox reaction does not take place. Graphite only acts as surface for transferring electrons. Hence, voltage and current produced is very minimal.

CONCLUSION

The concept of harvesting energy from living aquatic plants without interfering their growth is realizable. Plants can convert solar energy into electricity with the assistance of microbes around roots.

It is no doubt that voltage and current produced are affected by certain reasons. One of the reasons is the type of electrodes used. Inert and active electrodes give out different results. As for active electrodes, the greater the difference of electrode potential, the higher the voltage will be produced.

The type of plants is also one of the key elements. Aquatic plants are said to be the first choice due to their ability to survive in waterlogged situation.

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